

Leave No Trace: An Implementation Guide

Compiled by Bond Lammey & Lincoln Larson

2024

NC STATE
UNIVERSITY

College of
Natural Resources

Table of Contents

Introduction and User Guide	3
Audiences	3
Goals and Principles of Leave No Trace	4
Efficacy of Leave No Trace: Strategies that Work	5
Successful Implementation Efforts	7
Outdoor Recreation Center (ORC) at Washington State University (WSU).....	7
McInnis Canyons National Conservation Area (McInnis Canyons).....	9
Visit North Carolina (VisitNC).....	12
The Case for Leave No Trace	14
Communication Strategies	16
Conclusion	18
Appendix	19
Appendix A: Relevant References	19
Appendix B: Personal Communications	22
Appendix C: Challenges and Solutions from Case Studies	23
Appendix D: Summary of Key Resources	25

Suggested Citation:

Lammey, B., & Larson, L. (2024). *Leave No Trace: an implementation guide*. Raleigh, NC: NC State University, College of Natural Resources.

Introduction and User Guide

In a time when more people than ever are seeking to experience the great outdoors, administrators of outdoor spaces find themselves more resource-constrained than ever before. Operating under significant time and resource constraints, managers often struggle with activities that promote visitor involvement in preserving outdoor spaces for future visitors. The strategies that each organization adopts to address the toll that this increased human footprint takes on natural resources vary by site. Developing signage, creating physical barriers, providing education, and employing a volunteer workforce to monitor heavily trafficked areas are examples of these strategies. This is where [Leave No Trace](#) comes in. Leave No Trace is a 501(c)(3) (nonprofit) organization which was founded in 1994 as a collaboration between several federal land management agencies and the National Outdoor Leadership School to promote environmental stewardship practices and “develop and promote low-impact outdoor skills and ethics.”¹

Many facilities partner with the Leave No Trace organization to communicate Leave No Trace principles to program participants. Leave No Trace provides copious resources and low-cost methods to provide training to paid staff, volunteers, and visitors; however, adoption of Leave No Trace principles is inconsistent among outdoor organizations, especially those that manage “frontcountry” destinations. Frontcountry destinations are considered any location that is accessible by car or frequented by day users. These recreationists may be newer to the outdoors and are less likely to have exposure to Leave No Trace principles; therefore, they are less likely to follow these principles to preserve outdoor spaces. This implementation guide is meant to serve as a tool that:

- Reduces the barriers to Leave No Trace adoption among site managers and administrators.
- Promotes the benefits of Leave No Trace resources for reducing visitor impacts and improving outdoor recreation experiences.
- Demonstrates challenges in Leave No Trace implementation, as well as examples of successful implementation.

Audiences

The audience for this implementation guide are managers and administrators of public and private lands who wish to promote Leave No Trace principles and practices across a broader audience of outdoor recreation enthusiasts at their site and beyond. In terms of public lands, this includes administrators at National Park Service (NPS), Bureau of Land Management (BLM), US Forest Service (USFS), and US Fish & Wildlife Management (USFWS) sites, as well as state (e.g., state parks) and locally-managed sites. Private land administrators include

¹ Marion (2014), p. 10. [Leave No Trace in the Outdoors](#)

organizations that manage outdoor spaces that are open to visitors for free or for an entry/membership fee, such as adventure centers, golf courses, and camps. An additional audience for this guide includes destination management or tourism offices that seek to promote outdoor activities within a particular state or region.

All of these audiences interact regularly with frontcountry/day users who will mostly stay within 3-5 miles of a visitor center or parking lot and do not plan to stay overnight at the facility.² Because this population represents the largest group of outdoor recreationists and is likely to be least familiar with Leave No Trace principles, they are a critical target audience. There are also day users who have a cursory or casual familiarity with the principles of Leave No Trace and could be encouraged to better adhere to them. This guide aims to provide managers and administrators with reasons and strategies that promote understanding of and adherence to the principles of Leave No Trace.

Goals and Principles of Leave No Trace

The COVID-19 pandemic contributed to a rapid rise in tourism among national, state, and regional parks in 2020. One natural resource department “reported a 45% increase in state park visitors compared to 2019, with attendance surpassing the previous annual record in September 2020, and the number of ‘capacity closures’ (when a park has reached full capacity) reaching 260 in 2020, in comparison to 80 in 2019.”³ High volumes have continued into 2021 and beyond as new park visitors have discovered the joy of outdoor recreation and seek to continue their outdoor adventures.

From the National Park Foundation’s [Find Your Park](#) initiative⁴ to the linkage between tourism campaigns and outdoor recreation (most of the imagery on [Visit NC](#)’s landing page⁵ focuses on outdoor spaces across the state), spending time in the outdoors is now encouraged for even the most casual outdoor recreationalist. But this rise in visitation also creates unprecedented impacts on natural resources and corresponding management challenges.

The consequences of this dramatic increase in tourism, some of whom have little to no prior experience in the outdoors, have “resulted in trail and campground closures due to overcrowding, and the accompanying problems related to human activity” in popular protected areas such as Zion National Park and the Grand Canyon.³ These impacts have extended to many state and local parks as well, which may not have the capacity to cope with increasing visitor numbers.

2 Outdoor Industry Foundation. (2012). Outdoor Recreation Participation Report 2012. From: http://www.outdoorindustry.org/research/participation.php?action=detail&research_id=170

3 Bustad et al. (2022), p. 6-7. COVID-19 and outdoor recreation in the post-anthropause. From [Leisure Studies](#).

4 National Park Service. (2023). Find Your Park. Retrieved from <https://findyourpark.com/>.

5 Economic Development Partnership of North Carolina. (2023). Visit NC. Retrieved from <https://www.visitnc.com/>.

The field of recreation ecology aims to enhance visitor use management efforts by examining, assessing, and monitoring visitor impacts in protected natural areas and other outdoor spaces.⁶ Recreation ecology gained prominence in the 1960s after the passing of the Wilderness Act of 1964, which created guidelines regarding the protection of undeveloped land in an effort to minimize impacts associated with outdoor recreation. Today, recreation ecology continues to inform the way in which resources are managed. Fostering responsible stewardship behavior among outdoor recreationists is a key part of that strategy.

As tourism grows and impacts increase, it is important that new outdoor enthusiasts are exposed to Leave No Trace principles and have an opportunity to interact with these principles in impactful and prominent ways at all points of their outdoor journey. While this is an important goal, the behavior change and reach of Leave No Trace educational efforts are difficult to monitor and analyze over time. Popular frontcountry locations present challenges due to the high volume of visitor traffic and multiple entry points. All Leave No Trace efforts, including this guide, seek to influence behavior change over time for positive environmental impact.

Efficacy of Leave No Trace: Strategies that Work

Since Leave No Trace was developed, many studies have explored the efficacy of the program and adherence to the principles. Collectively, these studies reveal five themes that recreation professionals should keep in mind when implementing Leave No Trace:

1. *Any Leave No Trace signage helps:* A 2023 study that compared visitor response to different messaging regarding two Leave No Trace principles found that any type of signage performed better than the control group, or no signage at all.⁷ Signs that perform best are those with clear graphic elements that align with the intended messaging (for example, a picture of a muddy boot on a trail below large block text in contrasting colors that reads “Wipe your shoes”).
2. *Layer Leave No Trace into existing strategies:* A 2022 article⁸ combined direct management strategies (e.g., erecting scree walls and fences) with educational strategies (e.g., putting up signs) and found that strategies that involved direct management were most effective. However, researchers acknowledged that it isn’t feasible for these strategies to be deployed in all frontcountry areas. Strategies involving blended techniques (direct management practices + educational signs) also performed very well, and better than education alone.

⁶ Leung and Marion. (2000), p. 23. [Recreation Impacts and Management in Wilderness: A State-of-Knowledge Review](#).

⁷ Rice et al. (2023). The impact of graphic design on attention capture and behavior among outdoor recreationists: Results from an exploratory persuasive signage experiment. From [Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism](#).

⁸ Park et al. (2022). Efficacy of Combining Education and Site Management in Reducing Off-Trail Travel in a Fragile Biotic Community, Acadia National Park. From [Journal of Interpretation Research](#).

3. *Provide multiple opportunities for visitors to engage:* Many studies have found that the key to successful adoption of Leave No Trace principles is to provide visitors with a chance to see and internalize Leave No Trace content.^{8 9 10} This can include providing information about prominent website landing pages that frontcountry users may visit when seeking information about hiking trails or pavilion availability. It might also include actions such as (1) inviting interpretation and education rangers to add Leave No Trace-specific content (including links to the Leave No Trace website) when they develop and distribute junior ranger books and badges, (2) putting relevant Leave No Trace tips on maps that are distributed at visitor centers, and (3) placing Leave No Trace content at trailheads or other heavily trafficked areas.
4. *Encourage questions and reflection:* Most studies show that the more visitors are able to perceive that Leave No Trace has a positive impact on the environment, the more likely they are to adhere to its principles. One study suggested that those with a chance to engage with divergent viewpoints and reflect on their own perspective further encouraged adherence to Leave No Trace principles.⁹ For example, if a visitor does not see the value in keeping their dog on leash on a hiking trail, an effective strategy to encourage a behavior change is to engage in a dialogue with this visitor about the pros and cons of compliance and its impact on the natural environment. Placing rangers at trailheads a few times at the beginning of a busy season to communicate this message might reap larger dividends as it begins a practice of introducing Leave No Trace principles and inviting feedback from hikers before they set off on the trails.
5. *Don't reinvent the wheel:* Research indicates that while there is value in adapting Leave No Trace content based on different types of recreation activities (as certain principles apply more directly to certain outdoor activities), there is no need to adapt content specifically for frontcountry users.^{8 10} In other words, the principles of Leave No Trace don't vary based on activity, so including basic information about Leave No Trace is always a good option regardless of site type. There are many short, user-friendly versions of Leave No Trace guides (such as the infographic in the above **Goals and Principles** section) that provide facilities with a starting point to display information.

⁹ North et al. (2023). Leave no trace and sustainability education: Taking a dialectical approach. From <https://doi.org/10.18666/jorel-2023-11655>

¹⁰ Lawhon et al. (2019). Understanding attitudes and support for leave no trace: Informing communication strategies with frontcountry state park visitors. From <https://doi.org/10.18666/jorel-2019-v11-i1-9290>

Successful Implementation Efforts

Leave No Trace implementation can take many forms. The following case studies, based on interviews with organizations conducting Leave No Trace activities, highlight these unique perspectives. Participants were asked questions about examples of successful program implementation, including methods used and evaluation outcomes. They were also invited to share barriers to implementation.

Outdoor Recreation Center (ORC) at Washington State Univ. (WSU)

Organization type: nonprofit outdoor program at a public university

Location: Pullman, Washington

Description of Leave No Trace implementation/outcome:

At the ORC, which offers a variety of outdoor recreation experiences for university students, all overnight backpacking trips involve enough informal Leave No Trace training to qualify as a workshop. Training addresses specific concerns that relate to the activity participants are embarking on. For example, Dispose of Waste Properly is taught throughout the course so participants know how to pack and out food waste as well as human waste.

“When we are operating in the backcountry with groups, the biggest benefit of integrating Leave No Trace principles to know that not only is the group representing WSU operating ethically, but to know that the folks who go on those trips come away with more knowledge about how to ethically recreate outside.”
Paula Kimmerling, Adventure Facilitator

Evaluation methods:

Post-program surveys are distributed which ask the participants to rate their agreement with or understanding of specific topics. The two that relate to Leave No Trace (along with survey results) are:

- "I am more aware of the impact I have on the environment": 76% agreed, 19% said neither, and 5% disagreed.
- "I have a better understanding and appreciation for the outdoors": 91% agreed, 8% said neither, and 1% disagreed.

Articulated challenges/barriers:

Challenges the ORC faces when implementing Leave No Trace include:

- Facilitator turnover occurs at a high rate of 1-2 per semester, resulting in uneven interest and a constant challenge to keep all facilitators trained.
- Many program participants that follow Leave No Trace principles on the trip struggle to see how it applies to their everyday life outside of the course they are taking. There is a high level of adherence during ORC-sponsored trips, but a perception that once people are out in nature with their friends, they won't exhibit these same behaviors.
- WSU has a sizable Greek (fraternity and sorority) population. There are cultural norms within the "Greek system" that may be counter to the principles of Leave No Trace. For example, ORC staff have partnered with members of some sororities/fraternities to participate in litter clean up of "hotspots" on the Snake River. On one occasion, a fraternity member indicated a willingness to help, but only where he knew his fraternity was responsible for creating litter.

Relation to Efficacy of Leave No Trace findings:

ORC does an excellent job of drawing on existing Leave No Trace resources and layering Leave No Trace training into existing programming. However, ORC might do more to encourage questions and reflection among facilitators as they are trained, as well as the course participants themselves, which in turn would lead them to question their behavior outside of ORC excursions.

McInnis Canyons National Conservation Area (McInnis Canyons)

Organization type: federally managed land (via Bureau of Land Management)

Location: West of Grand Junction, Colorado

Description of Leave No Trace implementation/outcome:

McInnis Canyons is a vast area of public protected land (over 100,000 acres) administered by the Bureau of Land Management (BLM). This area contains “the second-largest concentration of natural arches in North America”¹¹ and has been the site of important fossil discoveries. Annual visitation volume is estimated at 300,000 people.¹² Leave No Trace content is integrated into McInnis Canyons’ signage, website, and site resource management plan (this plan is required for every BLM-managed conservation area). In 2023, McInnis Canyons received its designation as a Gold Standard site. There is a rubric involved in receiving this designation (see *Figure 1*), and after completing an initial assessment and some back and forth communication with Leave No Trace, McInnis Canyons made adjustments and received the designation. The areas in which they needed to improve were “On site messaging” and “Educational materials.”

“When we don’t have funding for seasonal staff to provide Leave No Trace trainings, we use CCA. They are directly in the community and are a great resource for us.” Dan Ben-Horin, Natural Conservation Lands Specialist, McInnis Canyons

¹¹ Bureau of Land Management. (n.d.). McInnis Canyons NCA. Retrieved from <https://www.blm.gov/programs/national-conservation-lands/colorado/mcinnis-canyons>.

¹² Koski, A. (2023). Annual manager’s report - McInnis Canyons. Retrieved from https://www.blm.gov/sites/default/files/docs/2023-08/2022-MCNCA_Managers_Report.pdf.

Evaluation methods:

In addition to the In Every Park Assessment (Figure 1), additional evaluation methods are informal, ranging from informal surveys of visitors when they exit the park to reports from law enforcement rangers on the number of tickets they issued for noncompliance. Due to its large amount of backcountry hiking trails and camp permits, the primary culprit being monitored is failure to pack in/out waste (primarily through wag bags).

Criteria	0	1	2	3	4
Staff (x2)	No staff have received Leave No Trace training	At least one full-time staff member has completed a Leave No Trace training at any level	Multiple staff members have completed any level of Leave No Trace training	Multiple staff have completed any level of Leave No Trace training AND at least 1 staff member is certified Leave No Trace Level 1 or Level 2 Instructor *	Multiple staff have completed any level of Leave No Trace training AND at least 2 staff members are certified Leave No Trace Level 1 or Level 2 Instructors *
Volunteers	No volunteers have received Leave No Trace training	Volunteers receive information about Leave No Trace or minimum impact practices as part of service	At least one volunteer member has completed any level of Leave No Trace training	Volunteer organization(s) working with the site have multiple members trained at any level OR at least one member is a certified Level 1 or 2 Instructor	Volunteer organization(s) working with site have multiple members who are trained at any level AND at least one member is a certified Level 1 or Level 2 Instructor
Training Opportunities	No Leave No Trace training is offered to staff and/or volunteers	Site encourages staff and/or volunteers to take the 101 Course or other Leave No Trace workshop	Site facilitates or makes available Leave No Trace training for staff and/or volunteer onboarding	Site facilitates or makes available Leave No Trace training for staff and/or volunteers annually	Site facilitates or makes available Leave No Trace training for staff and/or volunteers during onboarding and annually
On-Site Messaging	No on-site messaging related to Leave No Trace	Minimum impact information included on-site	On-site messaging sometimes includes a combination of minimum impact and Leave No Trace information, but it is not locally tailored	On-site messaging sometimes includes a combination of minimum impact and Leave No Trace information that is locally tailored	On-site messaging consistently includes a combination of minimum impact and Leave No Trace information that is locally tailored
Educational Materials	No educational materials related to Leave No Trace	Minimum impact information included in educational materials	Educational materials sometimes include a combination of minimum impact and Leave No Trace information, but it is not locally tailored	Educational materials sometimes include a combination of minimum impact and Leave No Trace information that is locally tailored	Educational materials consistently include a combination of minimum impact and Leave No Trace information that is locally tailored
Online Information	No online information related to Leave No Trace	Minimum impact messaging included in online information	Online information sometimes includes a combination of minimum impact and Leave No Trace messaging, but it is not locally tailored	Online information sometimes includes a combination of minimum impact and Leave No Trace messaging that is locally tailored	Online information consistently includes a combination of minimum impact and Leave No Trace messaging that is locally tailored
Programs	No programs that include Leave No Trace offered	Minimum impact information included in programs	Programs sometimes include Leave No Trace information, but it is not locally tailored	Programs sometimes include Leave No Trace education that is locally tailored	Programs consistently include Leave No Trace education that is locally tailored
Youth Education	No youth education programs that include Leave No Trace offered	Minimum impact information included in youth education programs	Youth education programs sometimes include Leave No Trace information, but it is not locally tailored	Youth education programs sometimes include Leave No Trace information that is locally tailored	Youth education programs consistently include Leave No Trace information that is locally tailored
Partnerships	Partner organizations do not include Leave No Trace in their work	Partner organizations utilize minimum impact information	One or more partner organizations sometimes utilize Leave No Trace education, outreach, or training in their programmatic efforts at the site	Site encourages partner organizations to include Leave No Trace education, outreach, or training in their programmatic efforts at the site	Site requires partner organizations to include Leave No Trace education, outreach, or training in their programmatic efforts at the site
Additional Sustainability Measures	Site does not currently incorporate sustainability measures	Site incorporates at least one sustainability measure such as: recycling or composting, single-use plastic mitigation, dark sky preservation, etc.	Site incorporates at least two sustainability measures such as: recycling or composting, single-use plastic mitigation, dark sky preservation, etc.	Site incorporates at least three sustainability measures such as: recycling or composting, single-use plastic mitigation, dark sky preservation, etc.	Site incorporates at least four sustainability measures such as: recycling or composting, single-use plastic mitigation, dark sky preservation, etc.

* Sites with more than 100 full time staff members should have 2% of staff certified for a score of 3 and 5% for a score of 4

Figure 1: In Every Park LNT Assessment (from <https://lnt.org/our-work/protecting-parks/gold-standard-sites/leave-no-trace-assessment/>)

Articulated challenges/barriers:

Challenges that McInnis Canyon faces when implementing LNT include:

- A lack of field staff to cover the vast landscape of McInnis Canyons is a significant challenge. As a result, site administrators rely heavily on partners such as Colorado Canyons Association (CCA). CCA provides much needed assistance with outreach, education, and programs such as their Adopt-a-Trail.
- Another challenge is a lack of public engagement in LNT practices, such as disposing of waste properly. This may be due to cultural norms attached to treatment of human waste. Essentially, people think it's weird to poop in a bag, so they aren't as likely to comply.

Relation to Efficacy of Leave No Trace findings:

McInnis Canyons does an excellent job of providing Leave No Trace signage and layering Leave No Trace into existing strategies such as the resource management plan. However, McInnis Canyons could provide more opportunities for visitors to engage with Leave No Trace. Admittedly, staff is spread thin and the team leans on CCA volunteers. It's likely many of these backcountry groups have a tour guide or unofficial group leader. If there was a way to better engage these leaders ahead of trips, it would lessen the burden on McInnis Canyons staff and CCA volunteers.

Visit North Carolina (Visit NC)

Organization type: state tourism bureau

Location: North Carolina

Description of Leave No Trace implementation/outcome:

Visit North Carolina (VisitNC) is part of the Economic Development Partnership of North Carolina (EDPNC) and was moved into economic development from the Department of Commerce less than ten years ago. VisitNC's main goal is to promote and market North Carolina as a vacation destination.

During the pandemic, leadership within VisitNC designed and launched [OutdoorNC](#) based on a model pioneered by [Care for CO](#). OutdoorNC involves prominent mention of Leave No Trace principles on the website. Another key strategy is providing access to a toolkit of materials including posters, videos, and online training for VisitNC's partner tourism sites and destination marketing organizations (DMOs) hoping to integrate Leave No Trace principles into their programs and messaging.

"We are starting to see a shift in behavior, or at least an understanding of behavior. The messaging on display by our destination tourism partners is having an impact." Heidi Walters, Senior Director, Partner & Industry Relations, Visit NC

Evaluation methods:

Surveys are distributed following social media awareness campaigns. These surveys ask people to gauge their awareness of, adherence to, and the importance of Leave No Trace principles. VisitNC has recently partnered with a tourism marketing company and expects to have better methods of evaluation in the future.

Articulated challenges/barriers:

Challenges that VisitNC faces when implementing Leave No Trace include:

- Ensuring that content is getting in front of audiences where it will have the most impact is a challenge.
- Another challenge is promoting Leave No Trace as a bipartisan issue that impacts all North Carolinians who recreate outdoors. VisitNC has partnered with a local government office, the Outdoor Recreation Industry office, to effectively communicate the message that resource protection and education are important across the political spectrum.

Relation to Efficacy of Leave No Trace findings:

VisitNC does a great job of layering Leave No Trace content within the existing OutdoorNC campaign, and of providing people with opportunities to engage with Leave No Trace content online and in person with partner tourism sites and DMOs. However, VisitNC could do more to ensure that Leave No Trace signage and messaging is visible online at multiple locations throughout the website and on social media. If the concern is that the right audiences aren't being targeted and the right message isn't being conveyed, providing more blanket coverage across audiences is a good step towards providing more visibility.

The Case for Leave No Trace

As the examples and case studies described above show, Leave No Trace can be an effective way to promote responsible recreation behavior. But how can site managers and administrators coping with visitor use management challenges make the case that investing in Leave No Trace education and messaging is worthwhile? Based on conversations with site managers, there are five key reasons that parks/facilities/affiliated organizations should continue (or expand on) Leave No Trace educational efforts.

1. **Reduce environmental impacts:** Visitors who abide by Leave No Trace principles are less likely to produce environmental impacts. Furthermore, by actively promoting Leave No Trace principles, sites will win over vocal outdoor enthusiasts who have a personal interest in keeping outdoor spaces clean. These enthusiasts will engage in conversations with friends who have less experience outdoors, creating a “trickle down” effect of Leave No Trace education and behavior modification.
2. **Reduce spending for waste removal:** Making visitors aware of principles such as “pack it in, pack it out” and “leave what you find” means that they will be more conscious of their consumption and waste habits (using fewer paper towels in a park bathroom, for example). Less trash on the trail and less waste in the parks means fewer maintenance rounds needed to manage park upkeep.
3. **Reduce instances of injuries:** Encouraging visitors to be more thoughtful about their outdoor experience if they “plan ahead and prepare” and could reduce risk and the likelihood of injuries. People familiar with Leave No Trace are more likely to make informed and appropriate decisions about attire, footwear, and equipment to bring and are more educated about the terrain for their outing. Another principle that aids in injury prevention is “travel and camp on durable surfaces.” Injury reduction also reduces spending waste as fewer employees are dispatched to treat injuries.
4. **Promote adaptive responses:** The field of recreation ecology is constantly changing, as is the knowledge of how to protect the environment. Sites that remain up to date on the latest Leave No Trace research will be positioned to protect and sustain natural spaces over time. An active partnership with [Leave No Trace](#) the organization will allow sites to get real-time information on scientific findings and advances related to Leave No Trace and figure out how to apply this at their unique sites.
5. **Promote staff recruitment, retention, and professional development:** Individuals who are newly entering the outdoor industry have an expectation that the organizations that employ them will be committed to conservation and sustainability, yet many of these individuals won’t have the budget to pay for Leave No Trace training out of pocket. Employers that provide this training for new employees will attract and retain top talent, providing them with professional development opportunities that facilitate a lifelong career in the outdoors.

What challenges can site administrators expect as they seek to implement Leave No Trace principles? While this guide seeks to demonstrate that the upsides of Leave No Trace implementation far surpass the challenges, it is unwise to assume challenges will not surface. The most common challenges based on the earlier case studies relate to ability to evaluate impact, budgetary concerns, increasing volumes of visitors, countering cultural norms, and staff turnover. These challenges, along with related solutions, are summarized in **Appendix C**.

The good news is that site administrators have anticipated these challenges, allowing them to proactively and creatively find solutions and continue to provide (or even expand upon) Leave No Trace offerings. The earlier case study section of this guide demonstrates some of their creative approaches to solving these problems.

Communication Strategies

By combining lessons learned from the **Efficacy of Leave No Trace** section, which examined strategies from published studies, and the **Successful Implementation Efforts**, which examined case studies of organizations that have successfully implemented Leave No Trace principles, five promising communication strategies emerged. Each strategy is paired with a specific Leave No Trace principle (or principles) to demonstrate how implementation might work.

1. **Incorporate visual elements:** As demonstrated in the **Efficacy of Leave No Trace** section, a 2023 study demonstrated that any signage is better than nothing. When putting up a sign about adherence to a Leave No Trace principle, create it as an easy to understand visual. Large text and contrasting colors helps (see *Figure 2*).¹³

Figure 2. Example of LNT Sign in DuPont State Recreational Forest, NC

¹³ Rice et al. (2023). The impact of graphic design on attention capture and behavior among outdoor recreationists: Results from an exploratory persuasive signage experiment. From [Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism](#).

2. **Create opportunities for participatory learning:** Some principles are best conveyed through exercises that help frontcountry visitors tangibly see their impact. Disposing of waste and leaving what you find are two great examples. During a hike or via a programmed activity at a natural gathering place such as a visitor's center, pause in an open space for a few minutes and distribute small waste bags. Invite participants to spend the next five minutes picking up trash and then reconvene. Compare how much trash each person was able to collect. Participants can also be invited to visualize if what they had gathered was natural to the space - how much of the natural area would they now be taking home with them?
3. **Utilize diverse and strategic distribution channels:** In some cases, incorporating signage and a physical presence of Leave No Trace messaging at crowded sites can be effective. In other cases, a virtual messaging campaign that has the potential to reach broader and more diverse before their trip might be preferential. Organizations should look at their annual calendar of events and align Leave No Trace messaging with existing times when high traffic is anticipated. For example, leading up to [Fat Bear Week](#) is the perfect time for the National Park Service to use social media to communicate bear facts that will help hikers and campers understand how to recreate in bear country (LNT principle "respect wildlife").
4. **Rely on and utilize existing resources:** [Leave No Trace](#) has a wide variety of messaging available, particularly for partner organizations such as those with Gold Standard designation. There are sub-topics based on type of activity (hiking versus rock climbing versus kayaking), based on age group, and based on duration of time or setting for training.
5. **Adapt messaging to the audience:** It is important to align messaging to the audience it is intended to reach. Activities that appeal to a troop of girl scouts may not work for a college fraternity or adults living in an urban neighborhood. Many groups interacting with the outdoors today have traditionally been underrepresented or excluded from outdoor spaces. Sites should adopt Leave No Trace messaging that is conveyed accessibly and inspirationally, not critically or judgmentally. The popular Leave No Trace strategy known as "Authority of the Resource"¹⁴ illustrates this strategy in action. In this example, a ranger explains why it is important for dogs to stay on leash (to ensure the local mule deer population is able to give birth without feeling threatened) rather than approaching a visitor and immediately demanding they keep their dogs on leash or risk being fined. Finding the right way to deliver a message will help people from different backgrounds understand why Leave No Trace principles matter - both to them and to the resource.

¹⁴ Wallace, G.N. (2018). Law Enforcement and the "Authority of the Resource." Retrieved from <https://lnt.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Authority-of-the-Resource.pdf>.

Conclusion

The principles of Leave No Trace address challenges that arise when humans interact with the environment. This implementation guide seeks to help site managers and administrators find the most effective and easy ways to implement Leave No Trace approaches for frontcountry visitors to their sites. There are many resources available that can be borrowed or repurposed to help an organization get started with Leave No Trace messaging and educational content.

In the course of compiling this implementation guide, several key themes emerged. The **Efficacy of Leave No Trace** section describes these in more detail, but encouraging takeaways include:

- 1) any amount of education and signage helps,
- 2) layering Leave No Trace strategies with direct management strategies is effective, and
- 3) the more chances visitors have to engage with content, the more likely they will be to internalize the messaging and adapt their behavior.

Site managers should use this guide and other Leave No Trace resources to identify messaging strategies that align with their context and management goals and experiment with new ways to promote and inspire environmental stewardship behavior among visitors to parks and protected areas.

Appendix

Appendix A: Relevant References

Boue, K. (2021). *#RecreateResponsibly 2021 Toolkit*. Google Docs. Retrieved from https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Oiidrri8UsTepwTDg4AkQP_6VEajLIPCNi5B45CNF7o/edit?pli=1.

Bureau of Land Management. (n.d.). McInnis Canyons NCA. Retrieved from <https://www.blm.gov/programs/national-conservation-lands/colorado/mcinnis-canyons>.

Bustad, J.J., Clevenger, S. M., and Rick, O.J.C. (2022). COVID-19 and outdoor recreation in the post-anthropause. *Leisure Studies* 42(1), 85-99.

Clark, B.G., Maples, J.N. and Sharp, R.L. (2020). Awareness and application of minimum impact practices among rock climbers in the Red River Gorge, Kentucky. *Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education* 23, 73–86.

Economic Development Partnership of North Carolina. (2023). Visit NC. Retrieved from <https://www.visitnc.com/>.

Jacobson, K. (2023). *Care for Colorado*. Colorado Office of Economic Development and International Trade. Retrieved from <https://oedit.colorado.gov/care-for-colorado-program>.

Koski, A. (2023). Annual manager's report - McInnis Canyons. Retrieved from https://www.blm.gov/sites/default/files/docs/2023-08/2022-MCNCA_Managers_Report.pdf.

Lammey, B. (2023, October). Leave No Trace implementation challenges. Unpublished manuscript. See **Appendix E** attachment.

Lawhon, B., Taff, B. D., Newman, P., Vagias, W. M., and Miller, Z. D. (2019). Understanding attitudes and support for leave no trace: Informing communication strategies with frontcountry state park visitors. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation, Education, and Leadership*, 11(1), 37–52. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18666/jorel-2019-v11-i1-9290>.

Leave No Trace. (2020, December 31). *Leave no trace for frontcountry - leave no trace resources*. Retrieved from <https://lnt.org/research-resources/leave-no-trace-for-frontcountry/>.

Leave No Trace. (2022, April). *Step-by-step - leave no trace*. Retrieved from <https://lnt.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Step-by-step-2022-fillable.pdf>.

Leave No Trace. (2023). *Leave no trace - home*. Retrieved from <https://lnt.org/>.

Leung, Y.-F., and Marion, J. L. (2000). Recreation impacts and management in wilderness: A state-of-knowledge review. In D. N. Cole ... et al. (Compilers), *Wilderness science in a time of change conference: Missoula, Montana, May 23-27, 1999: Vol. 5, Wilderness ecosystems*,

threats, and management (Proceedings RMRS ; P-15). (pp. 23-48). Ogden, UT: United States Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station.

Marion, J. (2014). *Leave No Trace in the Outdoors*. Mechanicsburg, PA: Stackpole Books.

National Park Service. (2023). Find Your Park. Retrieved from <https://findyourpark.com/>.

North, C., Berning, H., Karaka-Clarke, T. H., and Taff, B. D. (2023). Leave no trace and sustainability education: Taking a dialectical approach. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation, Education, and Leadership*, 15(1), 61–76. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18666/jorel-2023-11655>.

Outdoor Industry Foundation. (2012). Outdoor Recreation Participation Report 2012. Boulder, CO. Retrieved from: http://www.outdoorindustry.org/research/participation.php?action=detail&research_id=170.

Park, L. O., Marion, J. L., and Wimpey, J. F. (2022). Efficacy of Combining Education and Site Management in Reducing Off-Trail Travel in a Fragile Biotic Community, Acadia National Park. *Journal of Interpretation Research*, 10925872221133774.

Rice, W. L., Shellhorn, J., Bloomgren, V., Booth, L., Duncan, S., Elias, J., ... and Winckler, C. (2023). The impact of graphic design on attention capture and behavior among outdoor recreationists: Results from an exploratory persuasive signage experiment. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*, 42, 100606.

Schafer, D., Bobilya, A. J., Lawhon, B., Faircloth, W. B., and Schultz, J. (2022). Understanding hikers' behavioral intent towards leave no trace in Great Smoky Mountains National Park. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation, Education, and Leadership*, 14(4), 19–35. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18666/jorel-2022-11589>.

Taff, B. D. (2023). 20 years of Leave No Trace science and research - talking points. Unpublished manuscript.

Taff, B. D., Newman, P., Vagias, W. M., and Lawhon, B. (2014). Comparing day-users' and overnight visitors' attitudes concerning Leave no trace. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation, Education, and Leadership*, 6(2), 133–146. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.7768/1948-5123.1189>.

Taff, B. D., Rice, W. L., Lawhon, B., and Newman, P. (2021). Who started, stopped, and continued participating in outdoor recreation during the COVID-19 pandemic in the United States? Results from a national panel study. *Land*, 10(12), 1396.

U.S. Department of the Interior. (2023). *Fat Bear Week*. National Parks Service. Retrieved from <https://www.nps.gov/katm/learn/fat-bear-week.htm>.

VisitNC. (n.d.). *Make it your nature to protect North Carolina's outdoor spaces*. OutdoorNC. Retrieved from <https://www.visitnc.com/outdoornc>.

Wallace, G.N. (2018). Law Enforcement and the "Authority of the Resource." Retrieved from <https://Int.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Authority-of-the-Resource.pdf>.

Appendix B: Personal Communications

Interview with Dan Ben-Horin, Natural Conservation Lands Specialist, McInnis Canyons National Conservation Area, Zoom (2023, September 25).

- JD Tanner, Director of Education and Training at Leave No Trace recommended I contact Dan, who has been at McInnis Canyons since 2016.
- JD explained that McInnis Canyons just became a Leave No Trace Gold Standard Site, indicating that they've successfully adopted many Leave No Trace principles.

Interview with Heidi Walters, Senior Director, Partner & Industry Relations, Visit North Carolina, Zoom (2023, September 26).

- After noticing that VisitNC had some great resources on their [website](#) related to outdoor recreating and Leave No Trace, I reached out to Dr. Whitney Knollenberg (Associate Director of Tourism, NC State University) to see if she might connect me with someone who can complete the survey.
- Dr. Knollenberg suggested Heidi Walters, who founded the OutdoorNC initiative within Visit North Carolina, which launched in 2021.

Interview with JD Tanner, Director of Education and Training, Leave No Trace Center, and Derrick Taff, Associate Professor, Penn State University, Zoom (2023, July 14).

- I had a conversation with JD and Derrick in preparation for creating this implementation guide.
- JD represents the outreach and training portions at Leave No Trace.
- Derrick is a prominent researcher and academic on Leave No Trace topics, particularly evaluation methods, outcomes, and messaging successes. He provides much of the research data that is included on Leave No Trace's website.

Interview with Paula Kimmerling, Adventure Facilitator, Outdoor Recreation Center, Washington State University, Zoom (2023, September 20).

- Paula was one of my course mates during the Leave No Trace level two certification course and has worked in the outdoor field for many years.
- She has an expert grasp of Leave No Trace principles and has recently moved into a management position within the Outdoor Recreation Center at WSU.

Appendix C: Challenges and Solutions from Case Studies

Problem/Challenge Narrative	Solution
Uncertain/unable to effectively track impact of Leave No Trace activities.	Develop quantitative and qualitative assessment methods and implement surveys to allow visitors to self-report adherence.
Inadequate budget for Leave No Trace in comparison with other facility priorities.	Negotiate mutually beneficial agreements with partners, including nonprofits and government agencies; embed Leave No Trace activities within job expectations.
Increase in environmental impacts following the COVID-19 pandemic.	Establish partnerships with Leave No Trace or other conservation partners for training and message distribution, both of which have proven effective at improving awareness of environmental impact among new outdoor recreationists.
Leave No Trace principles counter current cultural norms (picking up trash of others versus not littering).	Create new meaning around unpopular behavior changes. For example, ORC emphasizes the importance of picking up all waste on excursions (even if someone else created it) to reinforce the “Dispose of Waste Properly” principle as a lifelong practice.
Staff/trainer turnover and/or burnout.	Create partnerships with Leave No Trace to facilitate regular training opportunities for both experienced and new employees. Provide chances for existing staff to deepen their Leave No Trace knowledge by paying for level two training for staff at 2+ years of employment.

Problem/Challenge Narrative	Solution
Struggle to get the message right and connect the appropriate message to the appropriate audience.	Choose which principles are the most important to highlight for a given audience. For example, improper disposal of waste is a big problem at McInnis Canyon, so they focus on the “Dispose of Waste Properly” principle and spend less time on the others.
Inconsistent training, especially among existing staff.	Incorporate Leave No Trace training into standard training schedule for staff and volunteers. These can be conducted by Leave No Trace staff or for facility staff depending on the certification level of staff.
Not enough staff to cover the area under management.	Negotiate mutually beneficial agreements with partners – corporate, nonprofit, and government agencies - to assist as needed at the site.
Struggle to obtain buy-in from leadership.	Create a direct alignment between organizational mission and Leave No Trace principles, helping leaders see the multifaceted value of Leave No Trace efforts.
Struggle to convince government entities that Leave No Trace is a bipartisan issue.	Partner with external organizations to promote shared goals. For example, VisitNC worked with the Outdoor Recreation Industry office (a governmental office) to make Leave No Trace a lobbying/voting issue across both sides of the aisle, and to further connect voters with the importance of Leave No Trace via “Year of the Trail” promotional materials.

Appendix D: Summary of Key Resources

Clark, B.G., Maples, J.N. & Sharp, R.L. (2020). Awareness and application of minimum impact practices among rock climbers in the Red River Gorge, Kentucky. *Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education* 23, 73–86.

Summary: This article reviews self-reported knowledge of and adherence to certain Leave No Trace principles among rock climbers in the popular Red River Gorge (RRG) climbing area in Kentucky. Surveys were conducted in 2015 and questions were based on the Leave No Trace Attitudinal Inventory (LNTAIM), but adapted to be particularly relevant for rock climbers. The population of unique climbers in this region was estimated at 7,500 in 2015, up from 5,000 in 2002 (Clark et al, 2020, p. 77). The study found a “positive relationship between a respondent’s awareness level of minimum impact practices and their self-reported actions adhering...based on ones’ knowledge of Leave No Trace” (Clark et al, 2020, p. 73).

Why valuable for Implementation Guide: I was interested in reviewing this article as it reviews a specific population of recreationalists that has experienced significant population growth in recent years. The article mentions that many in this audience train for climbs at climbing gyms, so their first exposure to Leave No Trace elements is when they feel sufficiently trained to experience a “real climb.” This population is also likely to be considered frontcountry given many climbs can be conducted during the day with climbers returning to their homes/hotel rooms for the night. The means of data collection in this article was also relevant, as many Leave No Trace studies rely on participants self-reporting both their knowledge of Leave No Trace principles as well as their adherence to these principles.

Lawhon, B., Taff, B. D., Newman, P., Vagias, W. M., & Miller, Z. D. (2019). Understanding attitudes and support for leave no trace: Informing communication strategies with frontcountry state park visitors. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation, Education, and Leadership*, 11(1), 37–52. <https://doi.org/10.18666/jorel-2019-v11-i1-9290>

Summary: This article describes a study that was conducted in 2012 among three state parks in Wyoming. The focus was to gather data on frontcountry visitors’ perceived the appropriateness and effectiveness of Leave No Trace principles. Importantly, this survey did not ask respondents to indicate their level of awareness or adherence of Leave No Trace; instead, it focused on their perception of the principles. The study’s authors mostly explored if there are differences between attitudes towards Leave No Trace between parks. One hypothesis revealed a difference between parks: “the ANOVA showed statistically significant differences between respondents from the three parks regarding their attitudes towards the effectiveness of Leave No Trace practices (Lawhon et al, 2019, p. 46). Ultimately, the study concludes that it would be beneficial to expose visitors across parks to Leave No Trace communications.

Why valuable for Implementation Guide: In conducting research, the question has come up as to why some parks have enacted Leave No Trace communications strategies and others have not. The consensus in some planning calls was that the key to success was having a park volunteer or staff member who has knowledge of Leave No Trace principles and is enthusiastic about user adoption has incorporated these principles into the visitor experience and the park's educational framework. While Leave No Trace provides materials that differ based on type of activity (hiking, rock climbing, kayaking), it is important to know if strategies also need to be adjusted based on type of park. This study indicates that a standard approach across parks is likely sufficient.

Leung, Y.-F., & Marion, J. L. (2000). Recreation impacts and management in wilderness: A state-of-knowledge review. In D. N. Cole ... et al. (Compilers), *Wilderness science in a time of change conference: Missoula, Montana, May 23-27, 1999: Vol. 5, Wilderness ecosystems, threats, and management (Proceedings RMRS ; P-15)*. (pp. 23-48). Ogden, UT: United States Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station.

Summary: The field of research ecology has existed since the 1920s, yet "little progress has been made...to develop and expand permanent recreation ecology research programs" (Leung and Marion, 2000, p. 42). This article examines the research that has been conducted from 1985-2000 on "recreation resource impacts and their management in the United States" (Leung and Marion, 2000, p. 23). Leave No Trace is discussed in the context of the benefit of adopting visitor and site management actions to mitigate the damages of human-caused damage to wilderness areas.

Why valuable for Implementation Guide: This article provided a list of "strategies and tactics for managing recreation impacts to resources or visitor experiences" (Leung and Marion, 2000, p. 37) that is quite comprehensive and can be used across multiple Leave No Trace principles.

Marion, J. 2014. *Leave No Trace in the Outdoors*. Mechanicsburg, PA: Stackpole Books.

Summary: This book explains the rationale for each of the seven Leave No Trace principles, as well as providing helpful background information on the history of Leave No Trace and some of the strategies that are employed to encourage adoption, including samples of marketing materials used to communicate and promote Leave No Trace.

Why valuable for Implementation Guide: This was the foundational text used as I prepared to create this document. I will draw heavily from this resource for many sections, including the goals and principles, audiences, and communication strategies sections.

North, C., Berning, H., Karaka-Clarke, T. H., & Taff, B. D. (2023). Leave no trace and sustainability education: Taking a dialectical approach. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation, Education, and Leadership*, 15(1), 61–76. <https://doi.org/10.18666/jorel-2023-11655>

Summary: This article explores the critiques of Leave No Trace as an educational tool, most notably “that Leave No Trace ignores wider impacts that contribute to climate change and diverse world views” (North et al, 2023, p. 61). The authors of this article posit that while Leave No Trace has its drawbacks, it is the most effective means of communicating sustainable practices across a large and diverse audience, and it is most effectively communicated when recipients of these principles are invited to challenge their own perspectives and engage with different belief structures related to sustainability.

Why valuable for Implementation Guide: The recency of this article, as well as the central premise of the most effective means to educate people on Leave No Trace principles and their value, make it very relevant for user adoption. This article references many other studies, including a 2018 study that found that “Leave No Trace signage significantly reduced undesignated trail use with front-country day users in an urban open space” (North et al, 2023, p. 64). The introduction of a critical analysis of the principles of Leave No Trace, inviting recreationalists to test their knowledge by questioning the efficacy of specific Leave No Trace components, is a helpful framework. One concept mentioned is “a new approach ‘Beyond Leave No Trace’ which... reframes [Leave No Trace] so that recreationists become active producers of new knowledge and collaborators in the educational process” (Simon and Alagona, 2009, p. 30, as cited in North et al, 2023, p. 65).

Park, L. O., Marion, J. L., & Wimpey, J. F. (2022). Efficacy of Combining Education and Site Management in Reducing Off-Trail Travel in a Fragile Biotic Community, Acadia National Park. *Journal of Interpretation Research*, 10925872221133774.

Summary: This study examined the efficacy of six different treatment approaches (in addition to the control group) to mitigating human-caused ecological impacts along a section of trail in Acadia National Park. Treatment approaches ranged from management-only techniques to education-only techniques, and also contained blended techniques. Adherence was observed via review of unobtrusive video cameras, then input and analyzed via SPSS. The most effective tactics were those that used direct tactics (management techniques such as erecting a low scree wall or fencing) over education-only or blended techniques. However, another notable finding was that “the number of seconds a visitor was observed to read the...educational signage messaging had a significant inverse effect on off-trail rates (Park et al, 2022, p. 40).

Why valuable for Implementation Guide: This study confirmed that education alone is not sufficient to protect most front-country spaces. To the extent possible, direct

management tactics (fencing, signage, boundary markers) play a vital role in ensuring protection of wilderness space. However, the longer recreationalists engage with signage, the more likely they are to internalize the information and react accordingly.

Rice, W. L., Shellhorn, J., Bloomgren, V., Booth, L., Duncan, S., Elias, J., ... & Winckler, C. (2023). The impact of graphic design on attention capture and behavior among outdoor recreationists: Results from an exploratory persuasive signage experiment. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*, 42, 100606.

Summary: This article seeks to understand the relationship between the design elements of Leave No Trace materials and adherence to these principles. The study created six treatment options for two different Leave No Trace principles and deployed them strategically at a popular hiking trail in Missoula, MT in 2022. The signs ranged from straightforward with no graphic elements to more conceptual in nature to a direct version that put the most desired behavior in the largest font and included a visual of the activity. Participants were observed for their interaction with the sign, as well as their adherence to the desired activity. In the case of both Leave No Trace principles, the direct version of the sign with the desired behavior in the largest font performed best. Another key finding was that “all treatments performed significantly better than the control conditions (no signage)” (Rice et al, 2023, p. 7). This article also found that the likelihood of a visitor to adhere to the Leave No Trace principle referenced increased the longer the visitor viewed the sign.

Why valuable for Implementation Guide: I almost didn't read this article, but I don't have a background in graphic design and thought it could provide a new perspective on how to effectively communicate Leave No Trace practices. I'm glad I read it! The article makes a strong case for the value of combining educational messaging with visuals that will help the messaging “stick.”

Schafer, D., Bobilya, A. J., Lawhon, B., Faircloth, W. B., & Schultz, J. (2022). Understanding hikers' behavioral intent towards leave no trace in Great Smoky Mountains National Park. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation, Education, and Leadership*, 14(4), 19–35.
<https://doi.org/10.18666/jorel-2022-11589>

Summary: This article examined the relationship between hikers at Great Smoky Mountains National Park and their behavioral intent on Leave No Trace principles. This intent looked at perceived appropriateness, effectiveness, difficulty to adhere to, and self-reported knowledge of LNT principles. The study was conducted via administering surveys at four popular hiking sites within GRSM in November/December 2021. One key finding was that “perceived effectiveness of Leave No Trace was shown to be a moderate to high predictor of hikers' intent towards five of the seven items” (Schafer et

al, 2022, p. 29). This supports earlier theories that perceived impact is a significant predictor of adherence to Leave No Trace principles.

Why valuable for Implementation Guide: The results from this study indicate that the guide should focus on demonstrating impact (or results) of practicing Leave No Trace behaviors. It also indicates that some principles need further clarification and/or demonstration of impact to gain adherence, most notably “travel through muddy spots to avoid causing additional erosion..., packing out all food scraps, and take breaks away from trails...as long as durable surfaces are available” (Schafer et al, 2022, p. 30).

Taff, B. D., Newman, P., Vagias, W. M., & Lawhon, B. (2014). Comparing day-users' and overnight visitors' attitudes concerning Leave no trace. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation, Education, and Leadership*, 6(2), 133–146. <https://doi.org/10.7768/1948-5123.1189>

Summary: This study relied on previously gathered data from a 2007 study about attitudes towards Leave No Trace principles among overnight visitors to Olympia National Park and conducted a similar study with day-users at Rocky Mountain National Park in 2009. Overnight participants completed a mail-in survey a month after their camping experience; whereas day-users were asked to complete a written survey on-site. Questions were modified for day-users to remove anything that was specific to backcountry or overnight stays. The study found that the perception of Leave No Trace principles between these groups “are largely congruent, and suggest that similar messaging approaches may be employed” (Taff et al, 2014, p. 133).

Why valuable for Implementation Guide: This study shows that Leave No Trace messaging that is currently employed and viewed to be effective for backcountry users can also be used for frontcountry users. While some items may need to be modified due to activity type or amount of time spent at a site, the messages don't need to drastically change from one audience to another. There is a possibility that day-users aren't as aware of Leave No Trace principles as backcountry users, which may impact the strategy to deploy this messaging - to a broader audience, with more frequency, distributed ahead of time when possible: “educational messages should be clear, concise, and occur early in the visitor's planning process (Taff et al, 2014, p. 142).